

Strategy for the Development of Pacu Jawi (Cow Race) Cultural Attraction as a Livestock Education Tourism in Nagari Pariangan Village, Tanah Datar District

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Abstract- *Pariangan village becoming known as a tourist destination. There was a cultural attraction called Pacu Jawi (Cow Race) in Pariangan Village, but unfortunately, the attraction has not yet been entirely developed, consequently, it has not given a comprehensive socio-cultural and economic impact to the main actors of Pacu Jawi activities. Pacu Jawi can be developed into a farm-based cultural attraction with the theme of educational tourism. This case study aims to to (1) analyze internal and external factors that support and inhibit the development of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions, and (2) determine the strategy of developing Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as a livestock education tourism in Pariangan Village Tanah Datar District. data was collected through literature study, field observations, interviews, and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) activities. The results show that the strategy for developing Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as a livestock education tourism in Pariangan village included: a). To conceive Pacu Jawi being an advance tourist destination with the theme of livestock education tourism outwardly leaving the cultural traditions and contents of existing local wisdom. b). Make the Pacu Jawi arena in a particular rice field which is conceptualized as a livestock education tourism c). The Government gives funding cows to be managed by ranchers (the main doers of Pacu Jawi attractions), which are maintained at the Pacu Jawi arena with the concept of livestock education tourism. d). Conduct exercise in Pacu Jawi cattle ranching to the younger generation. d). Conceiving legal regulations that can improve tourism activities that are sustainable and can protect culture, heritage, and local wisdom shape in the community. e). Making the activity of cultivating the fields, and culinary processing practices of cattle products as a livestock education tourism activity.*

Keywords- *Strategy, Pacu Jawi cultural attractions, Livestock Education Tourism.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years tourism has become one of the fastest growing sectors of the world's economy and it is widely recognised for its contribution to regional and national economic development. The tourism industry plays a role in social and economic development in all countries. Tourism is an activity carried out by a person or group of people by visiting certain places that are supported by various facilities for recreational purposes, or exploring destination objects, in a temporary period (Ismayanti, 2010).

Tanah Datar District is located in West Sumatra Province, with a vast area of 133,600 Ha (1,336 km²). The population of

Tanah Datar District according to the Central Bureau of Statistics Republic of Indonesia in 2018 was 370,993 people, Tanah Datar district consisted of 14 sub-districts and 75 villages. Tanah Datar District is an agricultural area, more than 70% of the population works in the agriculture sector. a tourist location in Tanah Datar District has the potential to be developed is Pariangan village, located in Pariangan District ± 13 Km from Batusangkar City. The tourism potential of Pariangan Village is nature tourism and cultural tourism

In 2012 Pariangan village chosen as one of the sixteenth most charming villages in the world according to the United States tourism media, the Travel Budget magazine, this effect can increase good promotion and influence tourists to visits Pariangan villages. The government and the community consider this phenomenon as a great opportunity for tourism development in Pariangan village. Pariangan Village has a cultural attraction called Pacu Jawi. according to Suzanti, (2014) based on the history, Pacu Jawi beginning from Pariangan Village then became developed in four sub-districts in Tanah Datar: Sungai Tarab sub-district, Pariangan sub-district, Lima Kaum sub-district, and Rambatan sub-district. However, at present, the management of Pacu Jawi tourism activities in Pariangan Village has not been seriously developed so that Pariangan village does not become the main tourist destination in the Tanah Tanah district even though the Pacu Jawi cultural attractions are unique and favored by tourists.

Pacu Jawi has great potential to be developed as a tourism event, as evidenced by the great enthusiasm of tourists who come to witness the Pacu Jawi Cultural Attraction. Pacu Jawi Cultural Attractions can be packaged in a livestock educational tourism activity and can increase the role and function of livestock as a commodity of cultural attractions (entertainment), as well as providing added value to farmers and Pacu Jawi cattle owners.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted to identify internal and external factors comprising strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) in the development of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as livestock education tourism in Pariangan Village,

then to choose a strategy for developing Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as livestock education tourism in Pariangan village.

The research was conducted to classify internal and external factors including strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the development of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as livestock education tourism in Pariangan Village, then to determine a strategy for developing Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as livestock education tourism in Pariangan village. This research should provide input for local governments informing policies on developing livestock education tourism, then to stimulate economic growth, generate employment, and preserve the environment and implement the functions of cattle in the cultural attractions of Pacu Jawi, finally raising the economy of all shareholders in the Pacu Jawi activities, Conserving inheritances , customs, including local wisdom in Pariangan village

The research methodology consists of a descriptive design with a quantitative study approach. the method for data analysis is descriptive analysis and SWOT analysis. SWOT analysis is used to systematically identify the strengths and weaknesses of internal factors as considerably as opportunities and threats in existing external factors. The location of this study is in the village of Pariangan, Tanah Datar District. Data consists of primary data and secondary data. Data was collected from literature studies, conducted observations and documentation, in-depth interviews, and carried out a Focus Group Discussion activity. The subjects in this study consisted of: the government, perpetrators of Pacu Jawi activities, Pariangan village community, and all stakeholders

Data collected preference then be presented in an informative manner Data were interpreted by analyzing internal factors (strengths, weaknesses), and external factors (opportunities, threats) possible doing a SWOT analysis. SWOT analysis is one method of generating conditions and evaluating a problem, project or business concept based on internal (external) and external (external) factors, namely strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, this method is most often used in business evaluation methods to view for the strategy will be carried out SWOT analysis only describes the situation that occurs not only solve the problem (Rangkuti, 2004).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main issues inside strategies into improving tourism in Pariangan Village are The Authentic Minangkabau Heritage, where the Story Begin and three supporting concepts i.e; Folklore area Economy based on local skills and mindfulness-based heritage.

Relating to the Tanah Datar Government’s Tourism Development Master Plan Document, It is said that Pariangan Village, according to the Spatial Pattern Plan, Pariangan Village belongs to an area of cultural heritage, where there are places and spaces around traditional high-rise cultural buildings, archaeological sites and fields by certain geological formations, Regarding such as objects or locations, several locations in Pariangan Village can be refined as protected areas for cultural heritage, including the Tantejo Gurhano Grave and the Pariangan Inscription. The locus concerning some

development of tourist destinations is the availability and predisposition of accessibility, infrastructure, facilities to support tourism. Following is the variety of preferences in the development of Pariangan Village tourist destinations:

1. Availability and predisposition of accessibility to Pariangan Village
2. Availability of information, transportation services, and lodging reservations
3. the role of community-based tourism in the development of tourism
4. Increase of investment in tourism improvement.

TABLE 1. Number of Tourist Visits to Pariangan Village in 2016 – 2018

No.	Year	Domestic	International tourists
1.	2016	17.836	936
2.	2017	45.760	1.638
3.	2018	244.334	1.057

Source: Tanah Datar Tourism Office, (2018)

Livestock raising in Pariangan Village, Tanah Datar District is mostly practicing in conventional systems. according to Sugeng (2006), extending cattle extensively which is rearing cows in grazing sedentary farming patterns or in the forest. Considering the community is furthermore traditionally breeding livestock, the Pariangan Village farmers have implemented an Artificial Insemination marriage system. Because Pariangan Village is located on the slopes of Mount Marapi with fertile soil productivity and relative to medium rainfall, the availability of forage grass in Pariangan Village is quite available, farmers plant grass in the fields or get from field grass. Cow's population in Nagari Pariangan can be seen in the following table.

TABLE 2. Cow and Buffalo Cattle Populations in Pariangan Village

No.	Kind of Cattle	Male	Female	Total
1.	Cow	540	9	549
2.	Buffalo	2	6	8

Source: Tanah Datar Agriculture Office, (2018)

Pacu Jawi (cow racing) is a traditional attraction that is performed after rice harvest, in the formation of a pair of cows in the fields spur watery and muddy. This activity has become a community tradition that survives in four districts; the Sungai Tarab sub-district, the Pariangan sub-district, the Lima Kaum sub-district, and Rambatan sub-district (Suzanti, 2014). The types of cattle used for Pacu Jawi have generally castrated cows. To determine whether a cow is good or not to race certain knowledge is needed here in choosing the cow, and is only possessed by certain people, usually, the factors to be considered include proportional body shape, cow agility, and some others characteristics.

Pacu Jawi's cows fodder is generally almost the same as the normal cattle feed system, a small difference is that the grass given is preferred if the cow is not too enthusiastic to consume grass, the grass is immediately replaced with another. Cows also supplied a special herbal tonic supplement before spurred. The cow must be scrubbed at least 2 times a week. The floor of the cage is made of bamboo, not using cement. However, cows need extra sun-dried outside the cage during the day.

For the people of Nagari Pariangan Pacu Jawi is not only a tourist attraction, but Pacu Jawi is a cultural tradition where they show their existence in the community, having Pacu Jawi cows is a symbol of economic prestige that they come from a wealthy family, then if their cows are able to perform with well then the family is also proud, meanwhile for Pacu Jawi jockey this attraction is an event to show their existence as a nimble and brave teenager.

A. Potential Tourism Development of Livestock eduTourism in Nagari Pariangan

Potential tourism destination is the attractiveness contained in an area to be developed as untapped or not managed well to become a qualified attraction and able to attract tourists to come to the area. Tourism education has been introduced as a special interest tour. Ismayanti (2010) argues that special interest tourism means tourism that offers activities that are not normally carried out by tourists in general or tourism with special expertise or interests. Based on field observations, it was found that there are several ecotourism potentials from animal husbandry activities in Pariangan Village, including the Pacu Jawi tourism object, in Pariangan Village farmers are still traditionally plowing rice fields used by cattle, then Pariangan Village also has several types of culinary derived from livestock products such as cow skin crackers, beef jerky, and beef rendang.

The Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) to the development of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as a livestock education tourism in Pariangan Village

TABLE 3. The Strengths and Weaknesses Factors

No	Strengths
1.	Pariangan Village is known as a historical and cultural tourist destination.
2.	Pariangan village has an unique cultural attraction known as Pacu Jawi.
3.	The existence of a Pacu Jawi society club (PORWI) that is already introducing Pacu Jawi attraction events in the tourism industry
4.	the activity of cultivating the fields using cows in the village of Pariangan and and there is a variety of culinary that comes from the processing of livestock products
5.	the local communities are still conserving their local heritage and culture significantly.

No	Weakness
1.	The Government of Tanah Datar districts has not yet focused on developing livestock tourism potential in Pariangan Village.
2.	some existence of a communal system of traditional communal land ownership in Pariangan Village is preventing the development activity.
3.	Tourism management has not been performed properly in Pariangan Village
4.	inadequate condition of regional infrastructure.
5.	The role of local communities in tourism management is still lacking in supporting tourism activity
6.	The tourism doers have not gotten a good impact from the implementation of the Pacu Jawi event
7.	The local government has not yet set regulations concerning tourism activities in Pariangan Village.

TABLE 4. The opportunity dan threat Factors

No.	Oppurtunity
1.	Pariangan Village have a cultural attraction called Pacu Jawi
2.	Pariangan Village is reportedly one of the most impressive villages in the world.
3.	An opportunity for promoting tourism activities by cultivating the fields using cattle and learning to make culinary products of livestock products
4.	The chance to increased tourism visits is achievable.
No.	threat
1.	The occurrence of social and economic conflicts in the local community from due to tourism improvement
2.	The decline in the point of local culture and the destruction in the role of existing local wisdom
3.	Pacu Jawi attractions can be raised to be brought out in other areas
4.	tourism activities that are becoming political aims

Analysis of Internal and External Factors consisting of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Weaknesses (SWOT) activities to improve Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as a livestock education tourism in Pariangan village can be seen in the following table 5:

TABLE 5. Internal Factor Analysis

INTERNAL FACTOR				
No.	STRENGTHS	Rating	Weight	Score
S1	Pariangan Village is known as a historical and cultural tourist destination	3,75	0,083	0,312
S2	Pariangan village has an unique cultural attraction known as Pacu Jawi	3,60	0,083	0,299
S3	The existence of a Pacu Jawi society club (PORWI) that is already introducing Pacu Jawi attraction events in the tourism industry	3,90	0,083	0,327
S4	The activity of cultivating the fields using cows in the village of Pariangan and and there is a variety of culinary that comes from the processing of livestock products	3,00	0,079	0,239
S5	The local communities are still conserving their local heritage and culture significantly.	3,80	0,085	0,324
Total				1,50
No.	WEAKNESS	Rating	Weight	Score
W1	The Government of Tanah Datar District has not yet focused on developing livestock tourism potential in Pariangan Village	2,55	0,074	0,189
W2	Some existence of a communal system of traditional communal land ownership in Pariangan Village is preventing the development activity.	3,30	0,082	0,272
W3	Tourism management has not been performed properly in Pariangan Village	3,25	0,081	0,266
W4	inadequate condition of regional infrastructure	3,90	0,091	0,358
W5	The role of local communities in tourism management is still lacking in supporting tourism activity	3,40	0,083	0,282
W6	The tourism doers have not gotten a good impact from the implementation of the Pacu Jawi event	3,40	0,083	0,282
W7	The local government has not yet set regulations concerning tourism activities in Pariangan Village	3,60	0,087	0,314
Total				1,96
TOTAL SCORE OF INTERNAL FACTORS				3,46

TABLE 6. Exsternal Factor Analysis

EXTERNAL FACTOR				
No.	OPPORTUNITIES	Rating	Weight	Score
O1	Pariangan Village have a cultural attraction called Pacu Jawi	3,60	0,114	0,410
O2	Pariangan Village is reportedly one of the most impressive villages in the world.	3,75	0,114	0,427
O3	The activity of Plowing paddy fields have not been developed well as a tourist activity	3,60	0,113	0,408
O4	Opportunities for Culinary tourism improvement	3,65	0,113	0,415
O5	The chance to increased tourism visits is achievable.	3,75	0,115	0,431
Total				2,09
No.	THREATS	Rating	Weight	Score
T1	The occurrence of social and economic conflicts in the local community from due to tourism improvement	3,70	0,114	0,422
T2	The decline in the point of local culture and the destruction in the role of existing local wisdom	3,50	0,110	0,385
T3	Pacu Jawi attractions can be raised to be brought out in other areas	3,80	0,093	0,354
T4	tourism activities that are becoming political aims	3,45	0,111	0,385
Total				1,54
TOTAL SCORE OF EKSTERNAL FACTORS				3,64

The results from the analysis of internal and external factors are then mapped into a space matrix. Based on the analysis table IFA and EFA can be calculated as follows:

- *Strengths – Weakness* = 1,50 – 1,96 = **- 0,46**
- *Opportunities – Threats* = 2,09 – 1,54 = **0,54**

Figure 1. The Matrix Space

The results of the space matrix in Figure 1, show that in supporting the development of livestock education tourism in Pariangan Village, the main strategy lies in quadrant II, the W-O (Weakness-Opportunity) strategy appropriates opportunities to minimize existing weaknesses. The main weakness is that the Tanah Datar districts Government has not given any attention to ecotourism in Pariangan Village, while the market

opportunity is still wide open, that many tourist requests who want to see Pacu Jawi tourist attractions. Strategies based on the results of an analysis of internal factors and external factors, including:

Strength-Opportunity Strategy

1. Making the cultural attraction of Pacu Jawi is a leading tourist destination with the thematic concept of livestock

education tourism by not leaving existing culture and local wisdom.

2. Making the exercise of plowing the fields and the motion of processing food produce from livestock as an alternative to livestock education activities.
3. Creating the concept of culinary tourism with the theme of animal tourism education.
1. Build a specific arena for the event Pacu Jawi attraction in a selected rice field with the concept of livestock education tourism.
2. Make regulations that can perform tourism activities better in Pariangan Village.
3. Involve the community to do fully active in tourism management
4. The local government provides livestock to the main actors of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions, then cows are gathered at communal breeding locations as cows for performances purpose
5. Performing the activity of plowing the fields using cattle, and culinary activities of animal produce processing being a livestock education tourism
6. Conceptualizing livestock education tourism packages related to Pacu Jawi attractions in the village of Pariangan.

Strength-Threat Strategy

1. Designing the tourism community group that preserves cultural values and local wisdom.
2. Attention is required to control by the local government to improve the welfare of the Pacu Jawi cows farmers.
3. Provide training for the improvement of Pacu Jawi cattle farming to the younger generation, and train them to become jockeys concerning cultural preservation.

Weakness-Threat Strategy

1. Creating several legal regulations that can regulate tourism activities that are sustainable and can preserve socio-cultural values in the community
2. Originating livestock education tourism activities being the main tourism activities, therefore, to increase more on the role of the community inside the scope of tourism.

Based on SWOT analysis, the values of internal and external factors continue determined, then choose some alternative strategies, to take some priority strategies, including:

1. Conceiving Pacu Jawi cultural attractions as a mainstay tourist destination with the theme of livestock education tourism without leaving the existing culture and local wisdom. Build a specific arena for the event Pacu Jawi attraction in a selected rice field with the concept of livestock education tourism.
2. The local government provides livestock to the main actors of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions, then cows are gathered at communal breeding locations as cows for performances purpose.
3. Involve the community to do fully active in tourism management.
4. Provide training for the improvement of Pacu Jawi cattle farming to the younger generation, and train them to become jockeys concerning cultural preservation.

5. Attention is required to control by the local government to improve the welfare of the Pacu Jawi cows farmers.
6. Creating several legal regulations that can regulate tourism activities that are sustainable and can preserve socio-cultural values in the community.

IV. CONCLUSION

The cultural attraction of Pacu Jawi can be manifested into a livestock education tourism, Some strategies towards developing the culture of Pacu Jawi attraction in Pariangan village include: Composing the culture of Pacu Jawi attraction as an attractive tourism object, because it is unique and only exists in Tanah Datar District, on the other hand, Pacu Jawi is a longstanding society tradition. By promoting the culture of Pacu Jawi attractions as livestock education tourism, the strategies can create include: presenting a special arena for organizing sustainable Pacu Jawi events supported by the local government, improving knowledge about tourism management to the main doers of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions foster awareness about tourism, animal husbandry business management, then improvement of the function of local tourism institutions to conserve existing traditions, customs, and local wisdom, he government provides cattle assistance to Pacu Jawi cows farmers in supporting the development of the Pacu Jawi attraction culture as a livestock education tourism, leading to an increase in the welfare of farmers, adding to the function of cattle in cultural attractions. Then Creating policies and regulations relating to the development of Pacu Jawi cultural attractions and in the support of general tourism activities in Pariangan Village.

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